

Signal complexification

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Gabor [1] introduced a complex version of a real signal $S(t)$ as

$$Z(t) = S(t) + iH(t). \quad i = \sqrt{-1}$$

where $H(t) = \mathcal{H}(S(t))$ is its Hilbert transform. $Z(t)$ leads to the instantaneous amplitude via

$$A(t) = |Z(t)| = (S(t)^2 + H(t)^2)^{1/2}$$

but more importantly, to signal instantaneous frequency:

$$f(t) = d(\text{Arg}(Z))/dt$$

ostensibly by-passing the limitation on concurrent time/frequency estimation.

Now, Gabor complexification works primarily because $H(t)$ is orthogonal to $S(t)$; consider instead another path to get there.

First, let $R(t)$ be a time-reversed version of $S(t)$, intuitively though not literally $S(-t)$; the Gram-Schmidt (GS) procedure yields an orthogonal component $Y(t)$ to $S(t)$ as

$$Y(t) = S(t) - [(S(t), S(t))/(R(t), S(t))]R(t)$$

where $(.,.)$ denotes inner product. Clearly

$$(Y, S) = (S, S) - [(S, S)/(R, S)](R, S) = 0$$

hence $Y(t)$ is indeed orthogonal to $S(t)$.

As an example, one cycle of a sinusoid and its GS component were generated in OCTAVE using the above recipe:

```
t=0:.001:2*pi;;s=sin(t);,r=flip(r(s));,k=(s*s')/(r*s');,y=s-k*r;;Y=y/max(abs(y));
```

Displayed below is the sinusoid **s**; its (rescaled) orthogonal component **Y** matches $-\cos(t)$.

The exponential $\exp(-t)$ and its orthogonal complement are shown below; the code is:

```
t=0:.001:5;;s=exp(-t);,r=fliplr(s);,k=(s*s')/(r*s');,y=s-k*r;;y=y/max(abs(y));
```


With a new orthogonal companion in hand, a signal's complexification is

$$C(t) = S(t) + iY(t)$$

and should yield respectable estimates of instantaneous signal amplitude (IA) and frequency (IF). To that end, consider a simple AMFM signal of amplitude 3 and frequency 5: thus

```
d=.001;;t=0:d:2*pi;;s=3*sin(5*t);
```

Next, the GS component y , scaled to match the amplitude of $s(t)$, follows from:

```
r=fliplr(s);,k=(s*s')/(r*s');,y=s-k*r;;y=3*y/max(abs(y));
```

Note that $(s,y) = -2.1183e-12$. The complex signal is therefore

$$c = s + i*y$$

so the instantaneous amplitude and frequency are

```
a=abs(c); f=diff(unwrap(arg(c)))/d; % d is the sampling rate
```

All results are tiered below; s and y in the left panel; the right top panel shows the estimated IA, with IF below it, both matching the input signal AMFM parameters.

A less simple example is

```
d=.001;;t=0:d:2*pi;;s=exp(-t).*sin(20*t);
```

The usual route

```
r=fliplr(s);,k=(s*s')/(r*s');,y=s-k*r; y=y/max(abs(y));,c = s + i*y;
```

produced a step-function signal phase:

```
ph=unwrap(arg(c));
```

with a linear trend, plotted below.

The difference quotient

```
(max(ph) - min(ph))/2*pi = 19.754
```

is very close to the generated sinusoid's frequency (20). A linear fit in OCTAVE through the phase:

```
polyfit(t,ph,1)
```

yielded the slope estimate 19.632, again close to the input frequency.

The last example is a frequency-hopping signal; its OCTAVE code is below.

```
d=.001;;t=0:d:2*pi;;  
s1=sin(120*t);,s2=sin(160*t);,s3=sin(200*t);,s4=sin(140*t);,s5=sin(180*t);,s6=sin(100*t);  
s=[s1 s2 s3 s4 s5 s6];
```

```
blok=120;;  
last=floor(length(s)/blok);
```

```
for j=1:last  
cut=s(1+(j-1)*blok:j*blok);  
rev=fliplr(cut);  
k=(cut*cut')/(rev*cut');  
gs=cut-k*rev;gs=gs/max(abs(gs));  
com=cut+i*gs;  
ph=unwrap(arg(com));  
fr(j)=(max(ph)-min(ph))/(blok*d);  
end
```

Frequency estimates are plotted below.

Means of estimated RF step-values and errors are tabulated next; respectable results.

True RF	Est RF	Error %
120	119.28	0.60
160	158.68	0.82
200	198.49	0.75
140	139.01	0.71
180	178.54	0.81
100	99.28	0.72

Finally, as in [2], fractional variants of this new complex signal would evidently be available.

References

- [1] D. Gabor, Theory of communications, J. Inst. EE, vol. 93, Pt. III, 1946, pp. 429 – 457
- [2] A. Cusmariu, Fractional Analytic Signals, <https://zenodo.org/records/3953020>, 2020